

On The Theory Of ‘Adaptive Musicology’

Okeke, Ikedimma Nwabufo (Ph.D)

Department of Music
Nnamdi Azikiwe University, Awka
(08038562309; 08184030580)
(In.Okeke@Unizik.Edu.Ng; Ikedimma77@Gmail.Com)

Abstract

‘Adaptive musicology’ is a novel theory proposed by me, Ikedimma okeke (PhD. Music pedagogy), a research fellow in the Department of Music, Faculty of Arts, Nnamdi Azikiwe University, Awka, Nigeria in the quest for solution to the challenges of learning musical instruments among children and young learners. It is drawn from the ‘theory of adaptation’ in the field of Animal Biology which sees **adaptation** as ‘the development of physical and behavioral characteristics that allow organisms to survive and reproduce in their habitat’ (Encarta Dictionaries, 2009). For instance, the possession of gills, fins, scales, cold blood, and streamlined bodies by most fishes represent their adaptive features which aid breathing, swimming, balance, body temperature, and moving with minimum resistance in water respectively. Fishes do not find it difficult to breathe and swim in water because it is most natural and native to them. Lions, tigers, and cheetahs develop specialized dentition, sharp vision, and speed which enable them to adapt in the wild. It follows that by nature the fish is programmed to live in the water just as the lion in the wild. The fish cannot survive on land neither can the lion adapt successfully in the water even though it can manage to swim through occasionally. The adaptive features of these animals come from their respective genomes. Relating this to humans we also discover that human features regarding height, dentition, body shape, tongue size, lip structure, finger and toe size, lung capacity, musculature, intelligence, temperament, voice timbre, etc., are basically a function of their genome for various adaptations in life. Applying this theory to the learning of musical instruments, it becomes interesting to argue that the potentiality to excel in a given musical instrument is traceable to the individual’s adaptive features. That is, the capability to adapt successfully to the learning and mastery of a given musical instrument is native to the individual. Because every musical instrument poses peculiar challenges in learning, it becomes necessary for the learner to be prepared for such peculiar demands and to choose the musical instrument/s that he or she can naturally adapt to. The piano demands long, thin, and strong fingers and learners with shallow and short breaths, under-bite, and cleft tongue should be guided away from the brasses and woodwinds because of their demands for good breathing, tonguing, and embouchure.

Key words: adaptive musicology, adaptation, adaptive features, genome, musical instruments

Introduction

Musical instruments come in various shapes, materials, and mechanisms of tone production. Some are tubular, some are conical, while some defy conventional shaping. Some are blown, some plucked, and some struck, while some are fingered to produce sound. These peculiarities present challenges in learning the instruments. By virtue of their shape and mechanism of sound production, musical instruments demand certain physical and physiological soundness from the learners as criteria for learning and mastering them.

An analogy with sports will make the point clearer: just as the human physiological and physical build form the basic criteria in sportsmanship, music also presents a similar situation. Football requires people with strong limbs, and stamina for a ninety-minute active engagement, while swimming requires flexible legs and hands with good lung power to sustain its demands in the water. Every sport, as it were, presents the ‘adaptive features’ it requires from the enthusiast. Musical instrument playing is even more complex owing to the fact that they are numerous and each one appears with its peculiar features and difficulties. As a result, the physiological and physical preconditions for learning them are many and these are the concerns of this theory.

The Case of Vocal Music

This theory has been subtly operational in vocal/choral music but unfortunately has been neglected in instrumental music and as a result has created much frustrations for musical instrument learners. In vocal music, people are grouped as soprano, alto, tenor, or bass depending on the ambit or range of their voice which is demonstrated on the musical scale with middle C as the focal point.

The four basic vocal groups or parts named soprano, alto, tenor, and bass, along with the variants, mezzo-soprano and baritone, are distinguished by specific ranges and they are illustrated below:

Image 1. Human Vocal Ranges

Some people will manifest the vocal features for soprano and some for other parts and this is based on the principle of adaptability. Requesting a natural bass voice to attend to soprano lines would be frustrating because he lacks the vocal capability to adapt to that part. This principle has been ignored in instrumental music where learners are asked to pick at random any musical instruments

of their choosing or by the assignment of the teacher and this haphazard approach appears to be the reason for the frustrations experienced by musical instrument learners for ages. The random approach has been accommodated in instrumental music pedagogy because an empirical research on ‘adaptability’ for musical instruments is lacking and this is the focus of this theory.

Significance of the Theory

The proposing of this theory is imperative now owing to the awareness of the benefits of playing musical instruments and the upsurge in the zeal for learning musical instruments amongst children and people across the world. Musicologists and educators world over are increasingly becoming conscious of the place of learning musical instruments in the holistic development of the child. It behooves music educators then to properly guide children in choosing the appropriate musical instruments which they can adapt to for a fulfilling instrumental experience. The outcome of further research on this theory would be beneficial to musicologists, educators, instrument tutors, policy makers in education, music curriculum planning, and prospective musical instrument learners. The theory will also address the usual procedure and practice of random choosing of musical instruments by learners and the haphazard assigning of musical instruments to learners by instrument tutors without recourse to physical and physiological adaptability checks on the prospective learners.

Objectives of The Theory

The objectives of this theory are to address:

- The relationship existing between human physiology and musical instruments
- Why learners fail on some musical instruments and succeed in others
- The actual demands of musical instruments on learners.
- To identify the ‘human adaptive features’ for various musical instruments.
- To establish standard physical/physiological checks of adaptability for learning various musical instruments

Scope of The Theory

The theory affects the learning of all musical instruments but we are focusing on Western orchestral musical instruments at this stage. Western orchestral musical instruments are classified

as keyboards (piano, piano-keyboard, organ, etc.); strings (violin, cello,*guitar, etc.); percussion (jazz-drum, timpani, kettle drum, etc.); woodwinds (clarinet, *saxophone, piccolo, etc.); brass (trumpet, trombone, tuba etc.).

*These instruments are not regarded as part of Western Orchestral even though they are of Western origin.

The Nature Of Western Orchestral Instruments And Their Intrinsic Challenges

Musical instruments have been grouped and classified with regards to their material makeup and mechanism of sound production.

Generally all musical instruments, by virtue of their nature, demand some physiological attention and adaptability from the learner. We shall look at some of those demands as they emanate from different Western orchestral Instruments

- **Keyboards**

Keyboard instruments are musical instruments sounded by means of keyboard- levers of black and white notes spread across a board. They are the piano, organ, piano-keyboard, etc.

Image 2. Keyboard levers

The whole set of levers in pianos, organs, harpsichords, clavichords, and similar instruments are called keyboard, that is, a 'board of keys' or 'keys on a board' and these are what actuate the tone production mechanism. Each octave consists of seven natural and five chromatic keys, arranged as in the accompanying figure above.

Keyboard instruments require learners who have strong, thin, and long fingers to attend to the notes of the instrument. Although some other playing techniques and strengths such as, wrist and finger flexibility can be mastered over time through practice, the learner with short, fat, and weak fingers is seriously disadvantaged. The impediments might not be noticeable at the initial stage of learning but later when he or she desires to ascend to the playing of more difficult and challenging passages.

Image 2a. Good fingers for keyboard instruments

The picture above shows long, strong, and slender fingers which are required for effective learning and playing of the instrument.

- **Strings**

Stringed instruments have cords made of metal or any other material that are tied to the body of the instrument and played by strumming, plucking, striking, or bowing. Members of this family include the guitar, harp, banjo, mandolin, ukulele, violin, etc.

shutterstock.com • 639444037

Image 3. Stringed musical instruments

Stringed musical instruments require long and slender fingers for effective learning and playing. Long fingers are necessary because notes run down the body of the instruments from the head to the tail or base, and only long fingers can contend with that. Slender fingers are also required because of the way the notes intertwine around the body or frets of the instrument. Thick fingers would be a disadvantage because it will not allow the learner to pick the notes with ease rather it would overlap the notes thereby producing undesired notes and chords. Another requirement for attending properly to the strings is long hands/arms. A relatively long hand would reach notes placed at the extremes more easily and faster than a short one.

Image 3a. Long and slender fingers required for playing stringed instruments

- **Percussion**

These are musical instruments that produce sound by being struck or, less often, scraped, shaken, or plucked. In more formal classifications of musical instruments, they are usually divided between membranophones and idiophones, with both categories including instruments

of definite as well as indefinite pitch. Some members of this family are, kettledrum, bass drum, wooden and metal gongs, cymbals, castanets, snare drum, conga, maracas, etc.

Image 4. Some percussion instruments

Although the instrumentation of almost all percussions is actuated by the hands, such as tapping, scraping, shaking, or striking with beaters, the actual energy that drives the activity comes from the biceps muscles located in the arms. Therefore, strong arm bones and muscles are relevant qualifications for good percussion learning and playing.

Image 4a. Anterior arm muscles

image 4b. Muscles of the forearm

The images above (3a and 3b) have helped to show the numerous muscles, tendons, and ligaments that are fused in the human arm. These muscles and their connectors power the entire hands. The implication is that the prospective percussionist must be imbued with healthy muscles and tendons and also be prepared to brace the physiological demands percussion instruments place on percussionists. Every other musical instruments demands some muscular activity from the arms but percussion instruments demand more.

Image 4c. Playing the jazz drum set

Playing the jazz drums, a percussion instrument, places even a greater physical and physiological demand on the player because of the involvement of the hands and legs. Both hands and both legs are active in playing the jazz drum as can be seen from the picture above and this involves serious muscular activity.

- **Woodwinds**

Woodwinds are wind instruments that have an enclosed, vibrating air column set into motion by a reed or by blowing across or through an aperture as distinct from brass instruments, in which the air column is set into motion by the vibration of the player's lips. Keyboard instruments sounded by the same means as woodwinds (e.g., the organ) are excluded. Despite the name 'woodwind', this group of instruments is no longer composed only of wooden-bodied instruments. Flutes, piccolos, and saxophones are now usually made of metal. Conversely, some early instruments made of wood, such as the cornett and the serpent, are not regarded as woodwinds because they are lip vibrated (The New Harvard Dictionary of Music, 1986). Examples of woodwind instruments are, the flute, recorder, clarinet, saxophone, oboe, bassoon, oja, ocarina, etc.

Image 5. Woodwinds

The basic technique for woodwind playing is the embouchure. Embouchure refers to the proper placement of the lips, facial muscles, and jaw in the playing of wind instruments (The New Harvard Dictionary of Music, 1986). Good intonation on a woodwind instruments demands correct embouchure. The basic lesson for woodwinds is simply embouchure and this must be learned before the student advances to other lessons and techniques of playing.

Image 5a. Correct embouchure for piccolo playing

Breathing Correctly: Use the corners of your mouth to breath. Maintain the correct embouchure biting pressure and flat chin.

Breathing Incorrectly: Many people completely open the mouth to breath, losing the embouchure and having to RESET many times over.

Images 5b & 5c. Correct embouchure and incorrect one for the clarinet respectively.

The nature of woodwinds requires a player with firm lips and strong tongue muscles for embouchure and tonguing.

- **Brass musical instruments.**

This is a family of tubular wind instruments or aerophones most often made of brass and sounded by the buzzing of the player's lips. Each consists of a more or less expanding length of tube with a mouthpiece at one end and a rapidly enlarging or flared opening called a bell at the other end. Common members of this family are the trumpet, cornet, horn, trombone, euphonium, and tuba (The New Harvard Dictionary of Music, 1986).

Image 6. Instruments of the Brass family

Image 6a. Holding and playing the trumpet

Brass instruments, by virtue of their material makeup, are relatively heavy. The potential trumpet player, for example, should have strong hands for proper carrying of the instrument. Just as the case with woodwinds, firm lips and good tongue muscles are also required for buzzing on the mouthpiece and tonguing. Without these physiological prerequisites, good intonation on the instrument would be difficult.

Regarding the physiological requirements for playing the brasses, Hunt and Bachelder (1994) advise that:

Before pursuing the performance of a brass instrument or selecting appropriate candidates for an instrument, consider certain requirements: (i) proper lower and upper jaw alignment, (2) straight teeth, (3) lip formation conducive to vibration, and, (4) adequate muscular development of the lips. If any one of these four requirements is not met, performance on a brass instrument will be difficult, if not impossible (p.17).

Postulations On The Theory Of ‘Adaptive Musicology’

The foregoing discussions have aroused the understanding of some kind of varied adaptability which nature bestows on individuals with regards to their mental, psychological, physical, and physiological composition and which is essential for their survival in their habitat. It appears that everyone is born with intrinsic features and qualities to adapt to certain pursuits and preoccupations. This presumably explains why some individuals can successfully pursue careers in such fields as medicine, aeronautics, marine biology, astronomy, etc. by virtue of the ‘adaptive features’ which are native to them.

Relating this postulation to music, we find out that by virtue of our varied giftedness and build (adaptive features), some people excel in certain areas of musicology while some others prevail in another. In instrumental music, it appears that some people naturally adapt to certain musical instruments more than others.

There appears to be a ‘genome of adaptability’ which prepares one to excel in a given area but not in another. It is against this background that this paper proposes a theory of ‘Adaptation’ and this theory appears to hold the explanation for the affinity and choice of careers amongst human beings. Regarding music, the theory could be adopted as ‘adaptive musicology’ and might help explain the nature of various pursuits and specializations in musicology. In instrumental music, it also could help in resolving the controversies and confusion regarding the choice and learning of musical instruments.

Instrumental music tutors have observed with worry that in a class of about ten young violin learners, for example, four adapt very easily to the instrument and progress faster than the rest while the remaining six struggle through the entire program.

It follows that it is that genome that programs the lion into becoming a wild hunter irrespective of however we try to tame or modify it.

Relating this to human beings we also discover that human features of tallness, shortness, complexion, intelligence, temperament, health, shape, voice, are already programmed in the genes right from conception.

Adopting this to instrumental music, it becomes interesting to argue that the ability and dexterity to excel in a particular musical instrument are also coded in the gene. That is, ‘the capability and ability to adapt successfully to the mastery of a given musical instrument is native to the individual. Even though the musical talent is innate in the individual he or she still requires

some tutorship and practice for it to blossom. Practice is basic to learning any musical instrument but the degree of effort for mastery between the ‘adaptive’ learner and the ‘non-adaptive’ learner of a given musical instrument varies conspicuously. The learner with the natural adaptability for a given instrument learns and masters the instrument faster and easier.

The adaptive features for the learning and mastery of the piano are clearly long and strong fingers. The trumpet basically requires such features as good lips, strong diaphragm and lungs, and firm tongue.

Although this theory is still in its natal and experimental stages but if it pushes through, musicologists and instrument teachers would be able to conserve all the energy vested on haphazard choosing, learning, and teaching of musical instruments. The argument is simple and summarized as follows: ‘if nature bestows on an individual the potentiality to excel and adapt well on the trumpet; why keep experimenting on the violin’? It would be tantamount to trying to make the fish to survive in the wild.

Methodology

The methodology for the application of the theory for reliability is presented here in detail.

The procedure shall be the experimental in nature. Children and young learners shall form the samples for the research experiment. The population will be sampled in groups of about four for learning musical instruments from four families of Western orchestral instruments which will include the keyboards, strings, brass, and woodwind. Every group will start as ‘beginner class’ and will receive rudimentary lessons on the given instrument for a period of time. The groups will also be monitored for progress or regress within the period. Careful observation will be sustained for each group throughout the experiment to record levels of progress, regress, challenges, difficulties, and adaptability. The samples that showed improvement on their instruments within the period would be moved to the intermediate class and used as the control sample while the samples that showed little or no improvement would be retained in the beginner class and monitored again for the purpose of ascertaining the factors responsible for their little or no progress. If the sample completely showed no progress afterwards, it would be moved to another group of instruments as beginners to see if there would be any level of progress in the new group. This will apply to all the groups while the control model/sample is kept stable in all the respective

groups. The data from the progress/regress chart will be reviewed periodically and subjected to analysis for the inferential deductions on adaptability

Multidisciplinary Aspects of The Theory

The theory of ‘Adaptive Musicology’ draws ideas from various disciplines such as

- **Animal/Environmental Biology:** The theory of adaption which explains the survival of animals in their respective habitats forms the basis of the theory of ‘adaptive musicology’ which this paper proposes.
- **Human Physiology:** Human physiology shall form the main thrust of the research. Human physiology of the hands, arms, legs, lungs, mouth, tongue, dentition, brain, muscles, skeletal structure, body shape, etc., are all aspects of the theory.
- **Sports:** The principles influencing the physical and physiological criteria for the selection of individuals for various sports inspire what the theory is advocating for instrumental music.
- **Statistics:** Some statistical tools such as percentage, standard deviation, mode, mean, comparative scales, squares, quotients, coefficients, etc., are pertinent to the sourcing, measurement, management, and analysis of data for the adaptability checks.

Some Methods of Teaching Music to Children and Their Learning On ‘Adaptive Musicology’

Some methods of teaching music to children portray some traits of ‘adaptive musicology’. When children are encouraged to dance to music, or clap to rhythm, or swing their arms to tunes, they are actually engaging in the tuning of their body parts to adapt to complex musical engagement awaiting them in the future such as singing and playing of musical instruments.

Some of these methods like Dalcroze’s *Eurythmics* which emphasizes early activation and sensitization of the body parts is quite relevant to the present discussion. This argument is based on the premise that weak limb and muscle control are usually induced by muscular inactivity in childhood. This was captured clearly by Cammpbell and Scott-Kassner (2010):

In the world of children, music and movement are nearly inseparable from one another. Clear the room, set the rules, start the music, and watch the movement begin. Rochelle pirouettes like a ballerina to the light and whirling music of the flute. Ally glides like a swan to the cello’s melody. Nicolas hops, then jumps in one place to the dialogue of the clarinet and bassoon.

With the entrance of the brass instruments, Sally marches with her knees high and her toes pointed. Sean, Li, and Tommy strut forward with long legs overlapping, arms stretched across each other's shoulders. Jimmie jogs with an imaginary basketball to the pulse of the percussion section. Consuela and Trina find the pulse and clap hands, forward, backward, and upside down. Anna stands at the center of it all, conducting. Children love to move (p.119).

On the surface, the submission above looks like a mere narrative on children's reaction to the sound of music around them. But it actually captures the development of the body's kinesthetic energy through music as the words in the narrative suggest: 'glides, hops, jumps', 'marches', 'jogs', 'clap', and 'stands'. Also the body parts mentioned are filled with action and motion: 'marches with her knees', 'toes pointed', 'long legs overlapping', 'arms stretched', 'clap hands', etc.

The point here is clear: the physiological development needed for learning musical instruments are better activated in childhood through proper teaching methods.

Campbell and Scott-Kassner (2010) also reported that 'Movement ability and the psychomotor skills necessary for performance improve with advancing age. By third grade most children can accurately maintain a steady beat through tapping' (p.121)

A Deeper Look at The Dalcroze System

The founder of the Dalcroze approach was Emile Jaques-Dalcroze (1865-1950), a Swiss musician who served as professor of solfege, harmony, and composition at the Geneva Conservatory. His pedagogy originated early in the twentieth century as he experimented with approaches to ear training. He astutely recognized that, despite the advanced stages of technical proficiency that his students demonstrated through the playing of their instruments, notable gaps were evident in their musical abilities. Simple rhythms were wrongly rendered, and flaws in pitch and intonation were frequent (Campbell and Scott-Kassner, 2010).

Although the Dalcroze approach is three-pronged: eurhythmics, solfege (ear training, and improvisation but he would be ever remembered for his eurhythmics. One aspect of his eurhythmics involves rhythmic gymnastics that are geared towards activating the diaphragm, lungs, and articulatory functions of the mouth and tongue.

As reported by Cammpbell and Scott-Kassner, 2010, ‘as his eurhythmics approach evolved, students developed the muscular rhythms and nervous sensibilities that would allow them to discriminate among even slight gradations of duration, time, intensity and phrasing’ (p.45). The submission above is that the activation of the diaphragm and lungs improves articulatory functions of the mouth and tongue which ultimately enhance the musical discrimination of the various shades of duration, time, intensity, and phrasing. It follows that having healthy lungs, diaphragm, tongue, lips, mouth, and limbs is not enough; they need to be sustained for musical relevance through proper exercising even from childhood.

Some Human Physiological Defects and Their Implications for Adaptive Musicology

Blum (2000), reports that, ‘’ besides tendinitis and tendovaginitis, pathologies of the musician’s hand are not more frequent compared to the entire population. Still several pathologies reach significant pronounced importance through the specific professional requirements.’’

- **Underbite**

An underbite is a term for a dental condition characterized by lower teeth that extend outward farther than the upper front teeth. This condition is called a class III malocclusion or prognathism. It creates a bulldog-like appearance in the mouth and face (Wikipedia, 2019).

Image 7. Underbite

The person with the dental condition of underbite should be guided away from brass and wind instruments. The reason is clear: his dental structure cannot accommodate proper embouchure, lip buzzing, articulation, and tonguing peculiar to the winds and brasses.

- **Muscle Atrophy**

Muscle atrophy is a condition where muscles waste away. It is usually caused by a lack of physical activity. When a disease or injury makes it difficult or impossible for you to move an arm or leg, the lack of mobility can result in muscle wasting. Over time, without regular movement, your arm or leg can start to appear smaller but not shorter than the one you are able to move. In some cases, muscle wasting can be reversed with a proper diet, exercise, or physical therapy. (Wikipedia, September, 2019).

The implications of this condition are enormous for learning any musical instrument because of the fact that all musical instruments require various kinds of muscular activity for their activation.

- **Rheumatoid Arthritis**

This is a chronic inflammatory disorder affecting many joints, including those in the hands and feet. In rheumatoid arthritis, the body's immune system attacks its own tissue, including joints. In severe cases, it attacks internal organs (Wikipedia, 2019).

Image 8. Rheumatoid Arthritis

This condition creates serious impediments to learning any musical instrument because of the deformity it leaves on the fingers.

- **Cerebral Palsy**

This is a congenital disorder of movement, muscle tone or posture due to abnormal brain development, often before birth. Symptoms include exaggerated reflexes, floppy or rigid limbs and involuntary motions. These appear by early childhood (Wikipedia, 2019).

This condition places the patient at a disadvantage in learning musical instruments because of the challenges of muscular and reflex control

- **Contractures**

This is a physiological condition where muscles or tendons that have remained too tight for too long, thus becoming shorter. They develop when these normally elastic tissues are replaced by inelastic tissues (Wikipedia, 2019).

Image 9. Contractures

This condition is a permanent shortening of a muscle area, such as is seen in the tightest muscles of people with conditions like spastic cerebral palsy (Wikipedia, 2019). This condition clearly poses serious challenges for a normal life to the patient. Consequently, because musical instruments require handling as a basic step in learning them, this condition therefore places the bearer at serious disadvantage.

- **Dystonia**

This is an involuntary muscle contractions that cause repetitive or twisting movements. Dystonia may affect one or more parts of the body and sometimes the entire body. The condition can be mild or severe (Wikipedia, 2019).

Image 10. Dystonia

Symptoms of Dystonia

- Patient has a “dragging lag”
- Involuntary pulling of the neck
- Patient experiences cramping of the foot
- Speech difficulty
- Uncontrollable blinking patient feels pain and is exhausted all the time

This physiological condition renders the potential of learning musical instruments almost impossible because of the involuntary distortions and contortions of the muscles associated with it.

- **Dyspnea**

This is a subjective sensation experienced and described differently by patients but generally characterized by:

- Shortness of breath
- Unpleasant breathing
- Labored, difficult, or heavy breathing
- Uncomfortable sensation when breathing
- Unable to get enough air
- Breathlessness

- Air hunger
- Choking
- Suffocation

Source: J.L. Jameson, A.S. Fauci, D.L. Kasper, S.L. Hauser, D.L. Longo, J. Loscalzo: Harrison's Principles of Internal Medicine, 20th Edition Copyright © McGraw-Hill Education. All rights reserved.

Image 11. Dyspnea (Wikipedia, 2019).

People with dyspnea should be guided away from brass and wind instruments because of their intensive air demand. Even when one with the condition reluctantly or out of ignorance engages

on the winds and brasses; he or she would never achieve mastery because of the complications that would emanate.

The problems resulting from dyspnea is not particular to instrumental music but even to vocal music because of the role of the diaphragm and lungs in producing notes.

- **Fissured Tongue**

This is a benign condition affecting the top surface of the tongue. A normal tongue is relatively flat across its length. A fissured tongue is marked by a deep, prominent groove in the middle. There may also be small furrows or fissures across the surface, causing the tongue to have a wrinkled appearance (Wikipedia, 2019).

Image 12. Fissured Tongue

A fissured tongue can make it appear as though the tongue were split in half length wise. This makes it easy for doctors to and dentists to diagnose the condition. The middle section of the tongue is most often affected, but there may also be fissures on other areas of the tongue. A fissured tongue can occur in association with several disorders. It is usually asymptomatic (no symptoms are apparent) (Wikipedia, 2019).

Clearly a person with the condition of ‘fissured tongue’ should not attempt any musical instrument from the wind and brass families because of the technique of tonguing which is basic in playing

them. Such persons can make their choices from the strings, percussions, or keyboards which place no demand on the tongue.

Limitations of The Theory

There are some apparent exceptions and limitations to this novel theory and they are listed below:

- The major exception to the claim of the theory of adaptive musicology regarding musical instrument learning is that certain people have the ability to learn and master so many musical instruments in their life time and this negates the idea of adaptability to a particular musical instrument.
- It is difficult to ascertain when an individual has completed his/her physiological development in order to decide which musical instrument he/she can excel in.
- Practice is a sensitive factor that can alter a presumption regarding an individual's progress or regress on a musical instrument
- The theory appears to have taken a position of complete musical hopelessness for individuals with certain physiological dysfunctions but trends in music therapy show evidences of various types of psychological and bodily restorations such as in cases of autism in children, Alzheimer, dementia, stroke, etc. through engagement in music – singing, music listening, drumming, and clapping to rhythm, etc.

Recommendations

The theory of 'adaptive musicology' is a novel one and requires time and proper application to stand through hence these recommendations:

- There is need for scholars, music educators, and musical instrument instructors to research more on the applicability and reliability of the theory regarding instrumental pedagogy.
- Further research should also be geared towards developing an empirical parameter for administering 'adaptability checks or tests' for learning musical instruments.
- Teachers of musical instruments should endeavor to draw a clear line between 'learning musical instruments for fun' and 'learning musical instruments for mastery'. The former does not require so much regimentation because the target of the learner is music

appreciation but the latter requires principled engagement, regimentation, and guidance to succeed.

Summary

This paper has captured the imperatives of teaching and learning musical instruments under the operation of the ‘theory of adaptive musicology’. The theory proposes that ‘the intrinsic nature of musical instruments demands that certain physiological criteria be met by prospective learners as prerequisites for learning and mastering them’. Keyboard instruments like the piano, organ, and piano-keyboard, for instance, require learners with long, slender, and strong fingers for the mastery; and learners with shallow breaths or underbite should be guided away from brass and wind instruments so that their pursuit would not be futile. It is hoped that the application of this theory will help in developing a standard parameter for choosing musical instruments and ultimately improve the standard of instrumental music pedagogy.

References

- Blum, J. H. (2000). *The musician’s hand: aspects of music physiology and performing arts medicine*.
- Campbell, P. S. and Scott-Kassner, C. (2010). *Music in Childhood*. USA: Schirmer.
- Child, D. (2004). *Psychology and the Teacher*. (7th Ed.). London: Continuum.
- Encarta Dictionaries (2009). Microsoft Inc.
- Gaurav, V., Singh, A. and Singh, S. (2015). Comparison of Selected Physical fitness Components among Male Football Players of Different Playing Positions. *Turkish Journal of Sport and Exercise*. Vol.17. Issue 2. Pp.22-25.
- Hunt, N. and Bachelder, D. (1994). *Guide to Teaching Brass*. USA: McGraw-Hill Higher Education.
- Leonhard, C.&House, R. W. (1972). *Foundations and Principles of Music Education*. New York: McGraw-Hill Book Company.
- Microsoft, (2009). Encarta Dictionaries.
- Randel, D.M. (1986). *The New Harvard Dictionary of Music*. Cambridge: the Belknap Press of Harvard University Press.

Internet Sources

http//: Wikipedia [Underbite]. Sourced: December, 2019

http//: Wikipedia [Rheumatoid arthritis]. Sourced: December, 2019

http//: Wikipedia [Dystonia]. Sourced: December, 2019

http//: Wikipedia [Contractures] Sourced: December, 2019

http//: Wikipedia [Dyspnea] Sourced: December, 2019

http//: Wikipedia [cerebral Palsy] Sourced: December, 2019